

Turbulence and power fluctuations in homogeneous unmoderated molten salt reactors

Ayoub Ouazzani^{1,2,*}, André Bergeron¹, Nathan Greiner³, Yannick Gorsse^{4,5}, Grégoire Allaire⁶

¹Université Paris-Saclay, CEA, Service de Thermo-hydraulique et de Mécanique des Fluides, 91191, Gif-sur-Yvette, France;

²Institut Polytechnique de Paris, Route de Saclay, 91128 Palaiseau, France;

³Université Paris-Saclay, CEA, Service d'Études des Réacteurs et de Mathématiques Appliquées, 91191, Gif-sur-Yvette, France;

⁴Université Paris-Saclay, CEA, Département de Modélisation des Systèmes et Structures, 91191 Gif-sur-Yvette, France; ⁵Stellaria Design, 17 rue Félix Esclangon, 38100 Grenoble, France;

⁶CMAP, CNRS, Ecole Polytechnique, Institut Polytechnique de Paris, Route de Saclay, 91128 Palaiseau, France

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ABSTRACT

Homogeneous molten salt reactors are a promising type of liquid fuel reactors, but they might suffer from power fluctuations related to the turbulent flow of the fuel salt, a behavior that has not yet been adequately studied. We present here a new framework to investigate the phenomenon. To simulate turbulent core dynamics, we combine a large eddy simulation model with a neutron diffusion model taking into account the transport of delayed neutron precursors. The models are implemented in the high-performance computing codes TRUST-NK and TrioCFD. The approach is applied to a simplified reactor core inspired by reference design concepts of molten salt reactors. We characterize the typical behavior of the system in terms of both average fields and deviations of local and global observables. In particular, with its intermediate turbulence level, we observe relatively low fluctuations of total power and average temperature in our system. We highlight the impact of the flow structure on the spatial distribution of power density deviations. We assess the sensitivity of the estimations to the energy group structure, showing that the amplitude of the fluctuations is not significantly impacted. Finally, we examine the scaling of fluctuations with average power, showing that relative power fluctuations decrease in amplitude with a higher power level.

Keywords: MSR, Turbulence, Power fluctuations, CFD.

1. INTRODUCTION

In a molten salt reactor (MSR), the fissile material is dissolved in a high-temperature molten salt. The nuclear fuel is liquid and travels through a circuit, carrying the heat produced in the core to a heat exchanger. The use of a liquid fuel offers potential advantages in terms of intrinsic safety, operability, waste management, resource management, and economic competitiveness [1, ch. 1-2][2]. However, this feature also comes with new challenges. In homogeneous MSRs, such as the Molten Salt Fast Reactor (MSFR) [2] or the Advanced Reactor for Actinides Management in Salt (ARAMIS) [3], the core is a large cavity with no internal structure. The salt is pumped at a high flow rate, leading to a turbulent flow in the core. This turbulent flow leads to fluctuations in temperature and density, resulting in fluctuations in neutron reactivity and therefore power, which themselves feed the temperature variations. A priori, this process is problematic, as local fluctuations of temperature might lead to material fatigue, and power fluctuations might undermine reactor control, or the effectiveness of standard methods of identification

*ayoub.ouazzani@cea.fr

of accidental power rise. While a crucial issue, specially for homogeneous MSRs, published studies on turbulence-related power fluctuations are currently limited [4][5][6, §5.3.1].

Studying the phenomenon requires capturing to some extent both the turbulent flow in a MSR core and the temperature-sensitive neutron flux. In this work, we study the core dynamics by performing Large Eddy Simulations (LES) coupled to a time-dependent neutron diffusion solver. We perform this type of simulation on a toy model of an MSR core inspired by the MSFR. We will briefly describe the models used, the software implementing them, and examples of simulation results.

2. MODELS AND NUMERICAL TOOLS

The TRUST-NK and TrioCFD software. To perform our simulations, we use TRUST-NK [7] and TrioCFD [8]. Both are extensions of the CEA open-source code TRUST for massively parallel fluid calculations [9]. TrioCFD implements various models for turbulent flows, including RANS (Reynolds average Navier-Stokes) and LES models. TRUST-NK on the other hand implements multi-group neutron diffusion and a simplified P_N solver, for both steady-state and time-dependent calculations, with or without transport of delayed neutron precursors (DNPs) and decay heat precursors. Thanks to their shared software platform, the neutronics–thermohydraulics coupling is specified in a single input deck, eliminating the need for a user-written coupling supervisor and minimizing user intervention.

Symbol	Description	Unit	Symbol	Description	Unit
ϕ	neutron flux	$\text{n.m}^{-2}.\text{s}^{-1}$	\mathbf{U}, U_i	velocity	m.s^{-1}
k_{eff}	neutron multiplication factor	-	p	pressure	Pa
ρ	reactivity	-	T	temperature	K
c	DNP concentration	m^{-3}	ν^t	kinematic viscosity	$\text{m}^2.\text{s}^{-1}$
v	neutron velocity	m.s^{-1}	β^t	thermal expansion coefficient	K^{-1}
D	neutron diffusion coefficient	m	λ^t	thermal conductivity	$\text{W.m}^{-1}.\text{K}^{-1}$
Σ	cross-section	m^{-1}	\mathbf{g}	gravitational acceleration	m.s^{-2}
ν	prompt neutrons per fission	-	c_p	specific heat capacity	$\text{J.K}^{-1}.\text{kg}^{-1}$
χ	neutron energy spectrum	-	ρ_m	mass density	kg.m^{-3}
β	delayed neutron fraction	-	Sc_t	turbulent Schmidt number	-
λ	DNP decay constant	s^{-1}	Pr_t	turbulent Prandtl number	-
q_f	energy released per fission	J	Q_v	volumetric flow rate	$\text{m}^3.\text{s}^{-1}$
\dot{q}	power density	W.m^{-3}	$\tau^{\text{SGS}}, \tau_{ij}^{\text{SGS}}$	sub-grid scale stress tensor	$\text{m}^2.\text{s}^{-2}$
P	total power	W	D_c	DNP diffusion coefficient	$\text{m}^2.\text{s}^{-1}$
Indices					
g	neutron energy group		r	removal	
l	DNP group		s	scattering	
f	fission				
Operators					
$\langle X \rangle$	time average of X		$\langle X \rangle_x$	space average of X	
$\sigma(X)$	standard deviation of X in time		\bar{X}	filtered X	

Table I. Notation and nomenclature.

Thermohydraulic equations. While density variations are crucial for neutron flux dynamics, from a hydraulic point of view, on our length and time scales, compressibility effects are negligible. Therefore, we assume incompressibility and use a Boussinesq approximation to model buoyancy, i.e. by a momentum source term $\mathbf{g}\beta^t(T_0 - T)$, where β^t is a thermal expansion coefficient, and T_0 a typical temperature. The filtered Navier-Stokes (NS) equations in our LES thus read:

$$\nabla \cdot \bar{\mathbf{U}} = 0, \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial \bar{\mathbf{U}}}{\partial t} + \bar{\mathbf{U}} \cdot \nabla \bar{\mathbf{U}} = -\nabla \bar{p} / \rho_m + \nu^t \nabla^2 \bar{\mathbf{U}} + \mathbf{g}(1 + \beta^t (T_0 - \bar{T})) - \nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\tau}^{\text{SGS}}, \quad (2)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\tau}^{\text{SGS}}$ is the sub-grid scale stress tensor which can be written as $\boldsymbol{\tau}^{\text{SGS}} = -2\nu_{\text{SGS}}^t \bar{\mathbf{S}} + \frac{1}{3} \sum_i \tau_{ii}^{\text{SGS}} \mathbf{I}$, with $\bar{\mathbf{S}}$ the filtered strain tensor $(\partial_i \bar{U}_j + \partial_j \bar{U}_i) / 2$, \mathbf{I} the identity, and ν_{SGS}^t a sub-grid scale viscosity that we estimate with the Wall-Adapting Local Eddy-Viscosity model [10].

The filtered temperature equation is naturally obtained with a diffusion-gradient hypothesis:

$$\frac{\partial \bar{T}}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\bar{\mathbf{U}} \bar{T}) = \nabla \cdot \left(\left[\lambda^t + \frac{\nu_{\text{SGS}}^t}{\text{Pr}_t} \right] \nabla \bar{T} \right) + \frac{\bar{q}}{\rho_m c_p}. \quad (3)$$

Neutronics equations. Recall that for liquid fuel reactors, the DNP's are transported by advection and diffusion. Since we are solving for a filtered velocity, we have in general to take into account the turbulent diffusion of DNP's due to sub-grid scale motion, which again can be modeled with a diffusion-gradient hypothesis. The filtered DNP equation thus reads:

$$\frac{\partial \bar{c}_l}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\bar{\mathbf{U}} \bar{c}_l) = \nabla \cdot \left(\left[D_c + \frac{\nu_{\text{SGS}}^t}{\text{Sc}_t} \right] \nabla \bar{c}_l \right) - \lambda_l \bar{c}_l + \sum_g \beta_l \frac{\nu^g}{k_{\text{eff}}} \Sigma_f^g \bar{\phi}^g. \quad (4)$$

For the flux, we use a diffusion model. Similarly to [11], we assume a linear variation of the macroscopic cross sections with respect to the density variations used in the Boussinesq approximation, and thus with respect to temperature.

$$\frac{1}{\nu^g} \frac{\partial \phi^g}{\partial t} - \nabla \cdot (D^g \nabla \phi^g) = -\Sigma_r^g \phi^g + \sum_{g' \neq g} \Sigma_s^{g' \rightarrow g} \phi^{g'} + (1 - \beta) \chi_f^g \sum_{g'} \nu^{g'} \Sigma_f^{g'} \phi^{g'} + \sum_l \chi_l^g \lambda_l c_l. \quad (5)$$

The flux equation will be discretized on a mesh that is coarser than the thermohydraulic and DNP equations, which justifies using the filtered fields, i.e. $\Sigma_i = \Sigma_i(\bar{T})$ and $c_l = \bar{c}_l$ in the above equation. Similarly, we assume that the power density in the temperature equation is given by $\bar{q} = \sum_g q_f^g \Sigma_f^g(\bar{T}) \phi^g$.

3. A TOY MODEL

Geometry. We model the core of a homogeneous MSR without external loops or heat exchangers. The truncated core therefore has a can-like shape, with 2.5 m in height and 2 m in diameter as shown in Fig.1. The lower and upper bands represent the inlet and outlet of the core respectively.

Thermohydraulic properties. We use properties inspired by the fluoride salt of a benchmark for multi-physics codes dedicated to MSR analysis [11], referred to as the CNRS benchmark. The properties are given in Tab.II. Notice that we choose a different viscosity value to increase the level of turbulence in the core. The resulting Reynolds number is 7×10^4 . This is still below that of the MSFR, which is about 10^6 [4, §2.2], making it less costly to simulate the flow in principle. As we are interested in general physical analysis rather than reactor design, we do not look here for a salt composition that would lead to the chosen values. One should bear in mind that there is a lack of empirical data on some salt properties such as the molecular diffusion coefficient of the DNP's D_c , or their turbulent Prandtl and Schmidt numbers. Expecting molecular diffusion to be negligible compared to turbulent diffusion, we take $D_c = 0$. And while we are planning to do a sensitivity analysis on the turbulent parameters, for now we choose arbitrary values below 1 for Pr_t and Sc_t .

Parameter	Value	Unit
ρ_m	2500	$\text{kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$
c_p	3075	$\text{J}\cdot\text{K}^{-1}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$
ν^t	4×10^{-5}	$\text{m}^2\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$
λ^t	0.5	$\text{W}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}\cdot\text{K}^{-1}$
β^t	2×10^{-4}	K^{-1}
Pr_t	0.85	-
Sc_t	0.85	-
D_c	0	$\text{m}^2\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$
inlet T	900	K
inlet $\langle Q_v \rangle$	4.25	$\text{m}^3\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$

Table II. Thermohydraulic properties.

Figure 1. Geometry of the can-shaped toy model.

Boundary conditions. For the neutron flux, to later assess the effect, if any, of a reflector on the target phenomenon, we impose vacuum boundary conditions on all boundaries in these initial simulations. The walls are adiabatic and impermeable for DNPs. At the outlet, we impose reasonable, arbitrary (but inconsequential) values of pressure, external temperature and external concentrations. At the inlet, we impose a fixed temperature and 0 DNP concentration. There is thus no recirculation of DNPs, which corresponds to the limit of long external loops. This, of course, leads to an underestimation of the effective fraction of delayed neutrons, which might worsen the stability of the core. However, its effect on power fluctuations will not be investigated here.

Concerning velocity near the wall, to not blow up the computational cost of the simulation, we use wall modeling at the fixed boundaries. However, TrioCFD does not provide LES-adequate wall models. The best option available is to impose a Reichardt profile [12], which is designed to estimate average velocities for a large range of wall distances. This means that typical turbulent instabilities generated in the boundary layer [13, §10.2] will be absent from our simulations. Given the relatively large dimensions of our core, we expect that these instabilities will not have an important impact on the estimation of power fluctuations. We leave it for future work to assess the validity of this hypothesis.

Finally, for the inlet velocity, since the incoming flow in a real core is already turbulent, a fixed profile would produce a qualitatively inadequate velocity field in the lower part of the core. Instead, we use a synthetic turbulence model. We generalized the model found in TrioCFD for homogeneous isotropic turbulence, so as to be able to generate stochastically a divergence-free unsteady velocity field which displays specified profiles of average velocity, turbulent kinetic energy and time-correlations. The model will be fully described in future publications. For an idea on the approach see [14, §3.1]. The imposed statistics is the same on all vertical sections of the inlet, making our model statistically invariant under rotation around the central axis.

Energy discretization and nuclear data. We used the neutronic properties of the CNRS benchmark, with its six energy group structure. But we also tried using a two group structure to test whether we can obtain similar estimations of power fluctuations while reducing the computation time for integrating the flux equation. To obtain balanced reaction rates between the two groups, we chose upper bounds at 0.02479 and 20.00 MeV. The macroscopic cross-sections of the two energy groups are calculated with APOLLO3[®] using a 1760 energy groups nuclear data library derived from JEFF 3.2, a self-shielding procedure based on Tone's method [15], and assuming a homogeneous infinite medium at 900 K. Similarly to [11], we limit the complexity of the reactivity feedback mechanisms by assuming cross sections which vary linearly with the density used in the Boussinesq approximation, without any Doppler effects.

Spatial discretization. We use two different uniform tetrahedral meshes: a coarse mesh of ~ 5 cm element size for the flux equation, and a finer mesh of ~ 2 cm element size for the other equations.

Temperature and power density are interpolated between the two meshes. The diffusion equation is discretized using a PolyVEF scheme, a new type of discretization that is currently being developed in TRUST. They are inspired by the PolyMAC discretizations [16], but they represent face-located vector quantities with all their components instead of their normal component only. The other equations are discretized using the VEF scheme [9, 17].

Initialization: adjusting the neutron multiplicity. To obtain a core that is critical close to the target operation point (with a target power level), given that we cannot fine-tune the parameters of the system beforehand, we divide the fission term by the corresponding multiplication factor: $\nu^g \leftarrow \nu^g / k_{\text{eff}}$. To find this value, we first perform a pseudo-transient of the thermohydraulic and DNP equations while regularly updating k_{eff} and the flux. We update them by solving the steady-state neutronics problem at fixed temperature and DNP fields, following the method described in [7]. When fluctuations of k_{eff} between updates become weak, we start integrating all the equations in time. Note that this does not guarantee obtaining the target power level exactly, since the retained value of k_{eff} corresponds to a perhaps typical, but nevertheless random, instantaneous temperature field. But *de facto* the average power obtained by this method deviates from the target by no more than 2%.

Time scheme and coupling method. At each time step, we integrate the thermohydraulic and DNP equations first. For that we use a semi-implicit scheme in which only the diffusion terms are evaluated at the next time step. This increases the size of the stable time steps compared to an explicit scheme without requiring to solve a heavy linear system—it turns out to be the best option cost-wise. After that, the flux equation is integrated with a fully implicit Euler scheme using the new values for the temperature and DNP concentrations interpolated on the coarse mesh.

4. A SELECTION OF RESULTS

Typical phenomenology. We first give an outline of the typical phenomenology observed in our simulations of the toy model. As an example, we give the results of a simulation where we aim for 0.33 GW of average power, and where we use the two energy group structure. The two meshes are partitioned into 256 zones, handled by an equal number of processors. The simulation times are of few hours per physical second. Fig.2 shows the average fields obtained. The power density has a standard shape for a core without reflector and vacuum boundary conditions. The velocity is highest in bands leading from inlet to outlet, and lowest in recirculation areas where vortices form. We confirmed this by looking at the Q-criterion [18]. The velocity and power profiles naturally lead to the temperature profile which displays low values in the high velocity bands and high values in the recirculation areas and within a widening column in the center.

Fig.3, on the other hand, shows the standard deviation of the fields, as indicators of the local variations. First, notice the asymmetry of the profiles, in particular in the relative deviations of power density, which indicates that the second-order statistics did not converge as much as the means on our simulated times. We can of course still draw meaningful results from them. The highest velocity variations are found, as can be expected, in the vortex-rich areas. The temperature variation is highest at the boundaries of high and low average temperature areas. We also notice two high temperature variation stripes at the center of the core separated by a low variation stripe. Animating the instantaneous temperature field reveals a small, apparent, radial movement of the central high temperature column. This movement results in this two stripes structure, as the axis is frequently covered by the hot column, while on shorter distances the temperature alternates between high and low values. These structures are found again, interestingly, in the relative deviation field of power density.

Fig.4 shows the dynamics of some global quantities. The reactivity is given by $1 - 1/k_{\text{eff}}(t)$, where $k_{\text{eff}}(t)$ is the instantaneous multiplication factor, computed as the ratio of the integrated production terms of the flux equation, over the sum of the integrated absorption and leakage terms. The reactivity fluctuates by 2 pcm, and the total power fluctuates by about 2%, with a standard deviation of 0.8% of the mean.

Figure 2. Average power density, temperature and velocity. For velocity, we represent the magnitude and streamlines.

Figure 3. Standard deviations of power density, temperature and velocity. For power, the standard deviations are normalized by the local average densities.

Figure 4. Time fluctuations of some global properties. The average power is $\langle P \rangle = 0.33$ GW.

Similarly, despite some stronger local fluctuations, the average temperature fluctuates by 0.2 K. As a reference, the fluctuations in the MSFR were estimated in [4] at 7.5%. It is therefore interesting to study the effect of different parameters on the amplitude of fluctuations. The difference in order of magnitude from the MSFR might come from, for example, the higher viscosity and lower Reynolds number in the toy model, or its mostly uniform temperature profile in the middle of the core. In this work, we only discuss in the last section a first parametric study relating to power level.

Sensitivity to group structure. The sensitivity of the total power fluctuations to the energy group structure is illustrated in Fig.5. At 3 GW, the obtained standard deviations in the two cases are similar, with 0.35% and 0.30% of the mean for the structures with 6 and 2 groups respectively. However, qualitatively, the fluctuations seem to display higher frequencies in the latter case. We leave for another

work the task of quantifying this potential difference and testing its robustness.

Scaling with power level. Fig.6 shows power fluctuations for three target power levels. We observe that the relative fluctuations decrease with a higher power. This means that the increase in absolute power fluctuations is sub-linear in the average power, a scaling that is non-trivial. While the general tendency is clear, the results do not let us conclude that the behavior is, for example, a power law, as Fig.6 also shows the sensitivity of the obtained curve to the duration of the sampling.

Figure 5. Power fluctuations for two energy group structures. The target $\langle P \rangle$ is 3 GW.

Figure 6. Power fluctuations for three different power levels.

5. CONCLUSIONS

This work represents an initial study of turbulence-related power fluctuations in a simplified model. We characterized its typical phenomenology in terms of average fields, space distributions of local fluctuations, and the dynamics of global quantities. We also established the scaling of total power fluctuations with power level and the sensitivity of their estimation to the choice of energy group structure. We hope to use this model to continue studying generic physical behaviors of homogeneous MSR, by estimating, for example, the effect on power fluctuations of other parameters such as viscosity and flow rate, studying the sensitivity to flow geometry, considering other statistics such as spatial correlations, characterizing in more detail the mechanisms leading to power and temperature fluctuations, and assessing the sensitivity to the neutronic model by using TRUST-NK's SP_N solver.

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